

Data-driven innovation requires complex eco-systems

CLINICAL CASES

Heterogeneous data

Heterogeneous computational systems

Complex workflows

Different tools

Heterogeneous and distributed databases

What is needed to efficiently connect the ecosystem?

- Standard formats
- Standard description of concepts (Ontologies)
- Standard and stable identifiers
- Rich, standard and machine-readable description of resources(data and tools) with metadata
- Clear access/privacy policies
- Technologies to deploy tools on different computational architectures
- Languages to easily connect different tools/data in workflows

Interoperability Platform

Develops and encourages the adoption of standards to describe life science data.

<https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/interoperability>

A curated, informative and educational resource on data and metadata *standards*, inter-related to *databases* and data *policies*.
<https://fairsharing.org>

Best practices, recipes, and guidelines to help you make your data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)

<https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org>
<https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/>

Markup models to improve the Findability on the Web of life sciences resources
<https://bioschemas.org>

Resolution service that provides consistent access to life science data using compact Identifiers
<http://identifiers.org/>

Data warehouse system that integrates biological data sources, making it easy to query and analyse data.
<http://intermine.org>

Open standard for describing analysis workflows and tools
<https://www.commonwl.org>

Recommended Interoperability Resources

Tools and registries peer-reviewed by a panel of external reviewers and identified as resources that facilitate the FAIR-supporting activities in scientific research

Annual open calls. New selected RIRs disclosed soon

[3DBIONOTES API](#)

Integrates multiple web services and an interactive web viewer to map biological annotations on structures

[BioImage Informatics Index](#)

A bioimaging resource finder based on biological questions, methods and tools

[BridgeDb](#)

Software framework and an API for mapping identifiers for related objects in life sciences.

[DisGeNET RDF API](#)

An RDF SPARQL Endpoint for DisGeNET, a knowledge platform on human disease genes and variants

[FAIRsharing](#)

A FAIR-supporting resource including a registry on data standards, repositories and policy

[FAIRtracks](#)

A set of JSON Schemas defining a draft minimal standard used to consolidate genomic track metadata

[g:Profiler](#)

A gene-centric data integrator with web UI and API services.

[Identifiers.org](#)

Provider of persistent and compact identifiers for data objects in life sciences

[InterMine](#)

Framework to integrate life sciences data based on an extensible data model

[ISA Framework](#)

Provides formats and tools to manage the experimental descriptions throughout the research life cycle

[MOLGENIS](#)

A flexible data integration platform to facilitate FAIR research data and accelerate scientific collaborations

[Omics Discovery Index \(OmicsDI\)](#)

Provides a knowledge discovery framework across heterogeneous omics data

[Ontology Lookup Service](#)

Repository for biomedical ontologies providing a single point of access to the latest ontology versions

[PLAZA](#)

Provides an integrative resource for functional, evolutionary, and comparative genomics in plants.

Main contributions of ELIXIR - IT

- Participation to the RDMkit through the participation to CONVERGE
- Bioschematization of different resources
- Definition of new BioSchemas types and profiles
- Definition of Ontology and other Interoperability resources for IDPs
- IntermiRMine: instance of InterMine datawarehouse dedicated to miRNA
- Italian COVID-19 Data Portal

Offered consulting activities

- Implementation of FAIR principles for data management
- Best practices and guidelines for data interoperability
- Development of protocols and ontologies for data integration

Interoperability Platform 2024-2028

The 3 Ps : Products, Processes, Practices

Continue building the FAIR Service Framework

Standardising **processes** for
FAIR data management

Interoperability Platform – Commissioned Services 2024-2028

Products: mapping and coordinating FAIR resources

WP2 Growing the FAIR-enabling portfolio of **products**

Redefine the procedures to categorise and assess products (RIRs)

Identify gaps in the current portfolio

Coordinate the long-term sustainability of Research Data Management resources

Minimise duplication of effort, capitalise on synergies, improve connectivity

Improve integration with other FAIR-enabling products (European Open Science Cloud framework)

Objectives

- Align and coordinate the development of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook
- Map out the landscape of FAIR-enabling products, including services and standards, within ELIXIR

Activities

- Coordination of the RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook in the wider context of the RDM ecosystem
- Establish portfolio of endorsed FAIR-enabling services and standards

Interoperability Platform – Commissioned Services 2024-2028

Processes: align products with user needs

WP3 Standardising **processes** for FAIR data management

Develop a common framework (requirements, recommendations, processes, resources) for successful FAIR-implementation across Nodes, Communities, and Projects

Aligning with EOSC and global partners

Curate a library of interoperability case studies

Standardise templates for outlining requirements and resources to be employed

Objectives

- Define the components of a common framework for interoperability
- Curate a comprehensive and well-organised library of interoperability case studies and use cases

Activities

- Converge communities around the use of a standard FAIR framework
- Collect a comprehensive library of 'Interoperability stories' from across ELIXIR (*Ivan Mičetić co-lead*)

Interoperability Platform – Commissioned Services 2024-2028

Practices: enabling users through the connection of resources

WP4 Establishing best **practices** for interoperable data management

Convert knowledge into actionable content

Empower user to navigate, select, and use the products; identify issues related to their application

Assess existing sources of training materials

Objectives

- Evaluate issues of interoperability that occur during actual data analysis or integration
- Conduct a use case-driven inventory of individual steps and complete workflows
- Assess the content of training materials provided by resources (TeSS, Galaxy, WorkflowHub)

Activities

- Engage RDM and technical experts to profile services, tools and workflows using FAIR data (*Flavio Licciulli co-lead*)
- Outreach, dissemination & training

<https://bioschemas.org>

A success story

Improves the Findability on the Web of life sciences resources

Structured data mark-up on web-pages, based on the definition of:

Types: vocabularies of terms that can be used to describe life science data on the Internet.

Profiles: community agreed layers over the vocabulary (e.g., are minimum, recommended, or optional properties)

ELIXIR-IT Contributions to profiles/types definition

RELEASED

- *Profile*: ComputationalTool (UniBO, CNR, UniPD)
- *Profile*: DataCatalog (CRS₄)
- *Profile*: Dataset (CRS₄, UniPD)
- *Profile*: Sample (CRS₄)
- *Type/Profile*: Protein (UniBO)
- *Type*: BioChemEntity (UniBO)

DRAFTED

- *Profile*: Event (CRS₄)
- *Profile*: ProteinAnnotation (UniBO)
- *Profile*: ProteinStructure (UniBO)
- *Type/Profile*: DataRecord (CRS₄)
- *Type/Profile*: LabProtocol (CRS₄)
- *Type/Profile*: Phenotype (UniBO)
- *Type*: BioSample (CRS₄)

Elixir-IT services annotated with Bioschemas

Sites: 10	IT		
Profiles: 3	Bioschemas	<i>International</i>	∨
Profiles: 5	DisProt	<i>UniPD</i>	∨
Profiles: 3	eDGAR	<i>UniBO</i>	∨
Profiles: 2	Galaxy Training Network	<i>International</i>	∨
Profiles: 2	ITSoneDB	<i>CNR</i>	∨
Profiles: 5	MobiDB	<i>UniPD</i>	∨
Profiles: 2	PhenPath	<i>UniBO</i>	∨
Profiles: 7	Protein Ensemble (PED)	<i>UniPD</i>	∨
Profiles: 1	RDMkit	<i>International</i>	∨
Profiles: 2	The Molecular INTERaction Database (MINT)	<i>UniRomaTV</i>	∨

Bioschemas for resource integration: IDP-central registry

UniPD

Curated from publications
2,038 protein entries

All resources have **Bioschemas** markup
embedded in data records

UniPD

Experimental and predicted
189M protein entries

UniPD

Deposition database
90 distinct proteins

Japan

Curated from publications
1,110 protein entries

SequenceRange

- rangeStart
- rangeEnd
- ...

SequenceAnnotation

Protein

IDPcentral Registry – Knowledge Graph generation

Bioschemas data dumps
transformation to a
Knowledge Graph

Concept merging

No need for custom APIs

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IDPcentral as a registry: <https://idpcentral.org/registry>

IDP Registry Knowledge Graph Home SPARQL

UniProt identifier Endpoint

3049 entries

Items 5

Genome polyprotein - [A0A024B7W1](#)

Zika virus (isolate ZIKV/Human/French Polynesia/10087PF/2013) **Taxon 2043570**

Resource	Entity ID	Sequence range	Sequence annotation
DisProt	DP03773	966 - 1065	disorder - IDPO:00076
		2396 - 2434	disorder - IDPO:00076 pre-molten globule - IDPO:00078 disorder to pre-molten globule - IDPO:00052 lipid binding - GO:0008289
		2927 - 2941	disorder - IDPO:00076
		2979 - 2992	disorder - IDPO:00076

RING finger protein Z - [A0A097F4I8](#)

Lassa virus **Taxon 11620**

Resource	Entity ID	Sequence range	Sequence annotation
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BioComputing UP - Department of Biomedical Sciences - University of Padua, Italy - 2023

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The IDPcentral registry:
(protein-centric)
view of IDP-KG

KG build from Bioschemas data dumps from three resources (DisProt/MobiDB/PED).

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